

The Empirical Testing of Organizational Citizenship Behavior(OCB) with Antecedent Servant Leadership, Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Commitment

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Abstract:- This study aims to determine and analyze partial effect of servant leadership, emotional intelligence, and organizational commitment on organizational citizenship behavior of PT. Jemla Ferry employees. PT.Jemla Ferry is a ferry service company located in Ketapang, Banyuwangi city. The design of study used explanatory research. Employees of PT.Jemla Ferry Ketapang Banyuwangi Branch were the population of study, with a total sample of 65 respondents. The sample technique was a technique used in sampling. The analytical method of this research uses multiple linear regression analysis with the help of the SPSS program. The results showed that servant leadership, emotional intelligence, and organizational commitment has a partially significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) of PT. Jemla Ferry Ketapang Banyuwangi Branch

Keywords:- *Servant Leadership, Emotional Intelligence, Organizational Commitment and Organizational Citizenship Behavior*

I. INTRODUCTION

Human Resources is a very important element in an organization on a large or small scale because human resources are seen as a very decisive factor in the process of organizational development. Human resources according to Saragih *et al.*, (2021) are the biggest investment for an organization, so it is very important to manage human resources or employees. Basically human resources become the center or spearhead for an organization to achieve goals more easily and quickly, especially if the company or organization is able to form and produce quality human resources. With quality and appropriate human resources will encourage or the implementation of good service.

One of the most important elements of service improvement is the behavior of the employee. According to Sari (2016) employees who behave positively within the organization will directly influence the services to be provided where this behavior is often referred to as Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is a voluntary action that goes beyond the basic needs of workers, such as helping co-workers who are not related to the compensation system and can benefit the organization (Kusumajati, 2014). OCB is an attitude or action of a person who is not the responsibility and part of it, which causes the organization to function effectively (Robbins, 2006:31). The factors that can affect OCB is servant leadership. Servant leadership is a management style in leading and serving at the same time and having a direct impact on the environment (Trompenaars and Voerman, 2010:3). Servant leadership can lead to OCB behavior because an employee will voluntarily do work outside of his responsibility if the employee feels valued, employees will feel valued if the leader treats employees like colleagues and gives employees the opportunity to express opinions without discriminating.

In addition to the servant leadership factor as a driving force for the emergence of OCB in an employee, emotional intelligence is also an important part. OCB behavior in the world of work something that only requires intellectual abilities, but in solving these problems emotional abilities or emotional intelligence are needed more. Emotional intelligence is different from intellectual intelligence which generally does not change, while emotional skills can be learned at any time. According to Robbins (2018) that emotions are not innate, but emotions need to be learned by individuals. If a person can solve problems in the world of work related to his emotions then he will produce better work. Individuals need to have emotional intelligence

because emotional conditions can affect thoughts, words, and behavior, including at work.

According to Goleman (2013), emotion is a mental condition that involves biological, psychological aspects, as well as a tendency to act. Therefore, emotions will affect the thoughts and actions of an individual. The link between emotions and one's behavior requires the individual's ability to be able to manage emotions well. Through the ability to manage emotions, an employee will feel and bring up positive emotions from within himself so that the individual becomes more sensitive and able to understand or empathize with other people and their environment, and can align the values adopted by their environment. Anthony (2015) stated that the higher the emotional intelligence, the better the employee's Conscientiousness. In contrast, Kappoda (2015) found that emotional intelligence has no significant effect on OCB. Atabaeva (2019) found that emotional intelligence affects OCB. Tofighi *et al.* (2016) found that emotional intelligence has no significant effect on altruism specifically.

Organizational commitment is considered to be an internal factor that influences the emergence of organizational citizenship behavior in employees (Prabowo and Setiawan, 2013). Organizational commitment is a condition when an employee sided with the organization, organizational goals and wants to survive being part of the organization (Robbins and Judge, 2009: 100-101). The formation of OCB cannot be separated from employee commitment to the organization, employees who are highly committed will be more loyal to the organization thereby increasing OCB behavior.

PT. Jemla Ferry is a company engaged in ferry transportation services for passengers, vehicles and goods. PT. Jemla Ferry is one of the ferry service providers that strives to create good service and prioritizes the safety of its users. PT. Jemla Ferry is included in the class of the best ships. Companies that seek to create the best service are driven by the desire of employees to work with high quality, which is a form of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) that is owned by an employee (Setyawan, 2021). Based on interviews that have been conducted with employees of PT. Jemla Ferry Ketapang Branch, it is known that most employees have suspected OCB, indicated by the positive behavior of employees where employees want to help fellow co-workers, able to carry out tasks without being ordered, and have high initiative when working. This allows employees to build solidarity and good cooperation. In this job, employees show teamwork when working to provide the best service while still prioritizing the comfort and safety of passengers. Employees give their best performance by helping each other and maintaining cohesiveness among employees while working so that they stay in line, so that the ship can sail properly and on time according to the time table set by the port authority. In this job, employees show teamwork when working to provide the best service while still prioritizing the comfort and safety of passengers. Employees give their best performance by helping each other and maintaining the cohesiveness between employees while working so that they stay in line, so that the ship can sail

properly and on time according to the time table set by the port authority. In this job, employees show teamwork when working to provide the best service while still prioritizing the comfort and safety of passengers. Employees give their best performance by helping each other and maintaining cohesiveness among employees while working so that they stay in line, so that the ship can sail properly and on time according to the time table set by the port authority.

OCB itself does not appear by itself, there are causes or driving factors. One of the causes in this company is servant leadership. Companies engaged in the service sector are required to provide the best service, and it is clearly stated where this company's vision is to become the best and most efficient service company that prioritizes comfort and safety. Providing good service will have an impact on the company's image, service delivery is not necessarily only carried out by subordinates. Superiors at this company provide important roles such as by setting a direct example to their subordinates, being friendly and mingling easily with subordinates, being able to listen to problems faced by their subordinates, and being responsive to complaints by their subordinates. Meetings are also often held for evaluation and given motivation and direction, here employees can convey the constraints experienced while working, this is where the interaction between superiors and subordinates takes place. This good interaction and communication can influence employees to behave OCB.

Organizational commitment has an influence on the emergence of OCB behavior. The organizational commitment of PT. Jemla Ferry employees can be seen when employees must continue to work and be responsible for their duties during national holidays or other holidays. Although some employees sometimes complain that they have to work during national holidays, employees do not complain about the situation or the company's work system. This proves the existence of employee OCB behavior in a company. The greater the organizational commitment to employees, the more loyal employees will be to the company so as to increase employee OCB behavior. Organizational commitment can also be seen when employees who always remain part of the company from contract status to being appointed as permanent employees.

Based on the description above, research will be carried out related to the influence of servant leadership, emotional intelligence, and organizational commitment to organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) for PT. JEMLA Ferry Ketapang Banyuwangi Branch

Fig 1. Conceptual framework

Based on the picture above, there are three hypotheses in the study, as follows:

- *Servant leadership* has significant influence on the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) employees of PT. Jemla Ferry, Ketapang Branch, Banyuwangi City
- Emotional intelligence has a significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) of employees of PT. Jemla Ferry, Ketapang Branch, Banyuwangi City
- Organizational commitment has a significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) employees of PT. Jemla Ferry, Ketapang Branch, Banyuwangi City.

According to Dennis (in Sari, 2016) states that the indicators of servant leadership are:

- a. Love
Emphasizing care, the attitude of a leader who does not hesitate to show care and attention to all employees
- b. Empowerment
Emphasizes the ability of leaders to listen to employees' opinions and entrust tasks and responsibilities to all employees
- c. Vision (Vision)
Emphasizes the ability of leaders to convey the vision or goals of the organization through providing motivation to employees to help become a better and more mature organization in the future
- d. Humility
Emphasizes the ability of leaders to appreciate and show respect, leaders who give appreciation to employees when employees are able to solve a problem or when doing a good job

- e. Trust
Leaders are able to make employees have confidence or trust in him. Rewards commensurate with the work done.
- c. *Promotions*, have the possibility or not to get career advancement while working in the organization.
- d. Supervision
The leader who pays attention to his subordinates and can provide direction and guidance.
- e. Co-workers
Relations between employees and their superiors as well as employees of other departments.

According to Robbins and Judge (2009) there are several indicators of organizational commitment, namely:

- a. *Affective commitment*, namely the organization seeks to increase emotional attachment between the organization and all employees by fostering a sense of pride and belonging to employees towards the organization
- b. *Continuance commitment*, namely the organization provides what employees need to develop, such as providing education or training that employees need.
- c. *Normative commitment* is an organization that seeks to provide employees with responsibility and freedom to contribute to the organization.

According to Organ *et al.*, (in Kusumajati, 2014) there are five indicators in OCB, as follows:

- a. *Altruism*(altruism)
The behavior of employees who are willing to help colleagues who are experiencing difficulties in terms of work, when their own tasks have been completed.
- b. *Conscientiousness* (far-reaching attitude) The attitude of employees who are responsible because they have done work beyond their obligations and provide performance that exceeds the minimum standard c. *Sportmanship* (tolerance) The attitude of employees who are able to make peace with less than ideal conditions or conditions in the workplace. Have tolerance

There are several indicators that encourage emotional intelligence, as follows:

- a. Recognizing one's own emotions, namely self-awareness or the ability to recognize feelings as they occur.
- b. Managing emotions, namely the ability to handle so that feelings can be expressed appropriately or in harmony until a balance is achieved within the individual.
- c. Self-motivation, namely the ability to manage emotions as a means to an end.
- d. Recognizing the emotions of others, namely the ability to recognize people is also called empathy. Individuals who have the ability to empathize are better able to perceive hidden social signals that indicate what others need out of their distress.
- e. Fostering a relationship is being able to recognize each individual's emotions and control them. Before being able to control other people's emotions, one must be able to control their own emotions and be able to empathize.

Individuals who are great at building relationships with others will be successful in any field that relies on smooth association with others.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used a explanatory research. Explanatory research is research that aims to explain the relationship between one variable and the other variables in the study. Employees of PT.Jemla Ferry Ketapang Banyuwangi Branch are the population of this study, with a total sample of 65 respondents. Saturated sample technique is a technique used in sampling. This study uses quantitative data types and primary data sources obtained from the respondent's answer questionnaire. The method of data collection, namely by distributing questionnaires, will be carried out directly to the employees of PT.Jemla Ferry with an agreed schedule. The analytical method of this research uses multiple linear regression analysis with the help of the SPSS program

III. RESEARCH RESULT

Based on the results of multiple analysis it can be explained as follows.

Table 1. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Variable	t count	t table	Information
Servant Leadership (X1)	3,780	1.99962	H0 is rejected
Job Satisfaction (X2)	2,744	1.99962	H0 is rejected
Organizational Commitment (X3)	2,605	1.99962	H0 is rejected

Source: processed data

In the table above, the following multiple linear regression equations are obtained:

$$Y = 4.212 + 0.321X1 + 0.237X2 + 0.333X3 + e$$

Shows if the constant of OCB is 4.212. The contribution of servant leadership to OCB was 0.321, the contribution of job satisfaction was 0.237, and the largest was 0.333 indicating the contribution of organizational commitment.

➤ t-Hypothesis (t test)

Testing hypothesis is done by conducting a t test which is used to determine the effect of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y). By comparing the value of t where if t count > t table then H0 is rejected, meaning that the independent variable affects the dependent variable and vice versa. Here is the result table:

Table 2. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Variable	t count	t table	Information
Servants leadership (X1)	3,780	1.99962	H0 is rejected
Satisfaction Work (X2)	2,744	1.99962	H0 is rejected
Commitment Organization (X3)	2,605	1.99962	H0 is rejected

Suger : Data processed, 2022

Based on the table above showed that the servant leadership variable (X1) shows that the calculated t value is greater than the t table, namely 3.780 > 1.999. Emotional intelligence (X2) shows if the t count value is greater than t table, namely 2.744 > 1.999. Organizational commitment (X3) shows if the calculated t value is greater than t table, namely 2.605 > 1.999. So it can be concluded that the variable servant leadership (X1), emotional intelligence (X2), and organizational commitment (X3) partially affect OCB (Y).

➤ The Effect of Servant Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior

The results of hypothesis test showed that servant leadership has a significant effect on the OCB of employees of PT. Jemla Ferry, Ketapang Banyuwangi Branch. This study showed that the indicators in the servant leadership variable, namely caring, empowerment, vision or motivation, humility, and trust have an influence on OCB.

Servant leadership here it can be seen that when superiors have concern for PT. Jemla Ferry employees, employees who feel cared for by a superior will feel happy and valued so that they can bring up OCB. Bosses who try to listen to employees' opinions and give full responsibility for their duties to employees can encourage OCB so that employees will show positive behavior and work well. Superiors who are able to motivate their subordinates to achieve the company's vision or goals that have been set can trigger positive behavior and OCB in PT.Jemla Ferry employees because employees are satisfied with the superior's way of conveying company goals through providing motivation, giving motivation is well received where employees will support and participate fairly in advancing the company.

Employees of PT. Jemla Ferry have a good perception of servant leadership. High and good servant leadership will encourage OCB behavior by employees. Employees who believe in their superiors and are appreciated will work more than usual. Employees who feel heard will also give their best opinions for mutual convenience and progress. This research is in line with research that has been conducted by Sari (2016), Suwandana (2017), Surya (2017), and Fuad (2021) with the results of servant leadership having an

influential and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior. However, this is not the same as the results of Setiawan's research (2013) which proves that servant leadership has no significant effect on OCB.

➤ *The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Organizational Citizenship Behavior*

The results of the hypothesis test show that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on the OCB of employees of PT. Jemla Ferry, Ketapang Banyuwangi Branch. This study shows that the indicators that exist in the emotional intelligence variable, namely the work itself, salary, promotions, supervision, and co-workers have an influence on OCB. Based on the value of emotional intelligence has a significant effect on OCB. In this study, it can be seen that the direct effect of the emotional intelligence variable on the OCB of Jember University employees is proven to be significant. It means that the third hypothesis which states that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on OCB, is proven. Based on the results of the respondents' assessment, it shows that emotional intelligence is well perceived by employees so that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on employee OCB. This is due to the emotional intelligence of employees at Jember University which will lead to good OCB for employees. Strong emotional intelligence will support agency goals.

The implementation of research results in terms of its relation to OCB explained that employees are the main element of human resources having a role that determines the success of the company. Therefore, an employee who is able to play this role requires competence, motivation, discipline and a high work ethic. Therefore an employee must have high emotional intelligence (Emotional Quotion/EQ) so that his feelings will be sincere and calm in carrying out his duties to provide the best service. This result is in accordance with Res *et al.* (2014), proved that there is a significant effect on the emotional intelligence variable on OCB.

➤ *The Effect of Organizational Commitment to Organizational Citizenship Behavior*

The results of the hypothesis test showed that organizational commitment has a significant effect on the OCB of employees of PT. Jemla Ferry, Ketapang Banyuwangi Branch, because the t count shows a value that is greater than the t table, namely $2.605 > 1.99962$. This study showed that the indicators in the organizational commitment variable, namely affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment, have an influence on OCB.

Organizational commitment showed that employees of PT. Jemla Ferry Ketapang Banyuwangi branch feels proud to be able to work there and a sense of belonging to the organization arises because the organization has provided welfare to employees. Welfare is in the form of a sense of security, comfort, and fulfillment of the needs that employees need when employees work. A sense of pride in being part of the organization and a sense of belonging to the organization shows that employees will contribute to achieving organizational goals by providing the best beyond standards

so that OCB behavior will increase in employees. Organizational commitment that seeks to provide responsibility and trust to employees,

Organizational commitment to PT. Jemla Ferry employees is shown by the phenomenon that employees there feel proud to be part of the company. This pride can be proven where employees retain their membership, employees have also spent quite a long time there as seen from the length of time most of the employees have worked for quite a long time. Employees of PT. Jemla Ferry perceive organizational commitment well. High organizational commitment will influence and encourage OCB behavior by employees.

These results support research conducted by Setiawan (2013), Prabandewi (2016), Riana (2019), and Yolanda (2020) that organizational commitment has a significant and significant effect on OCB. However, this is not in line with the research results of Lintong *et al.*, (2018) and Prasetyo (2021) which show results if organizational commitment has a negative and insignificant effect on OCB.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Servant leadership had a significant influence on OCB, so that if the servant leadership variable increases, the OCB of PT. Jemla Ferry Employees of the Ketapang Banyuwangi Branch will also increase. From the results of the description of the variables, it shows that employees value the servant leadership variable well with five indicators, namely, caring, empowering, visioning or motivating, humility, and trust. Employees who believe in superiors, are appreciated, feel listened to will work harder than the general standard so that it has an impact on organizational progress.

Emotional intelligence had a significant influence on OCB, so increasing employee emotional intelligence will also increase OCB in Employees of PT. Jemla Ferry, Ketapang Banyuwangi Branch. Evidenced by employees who perceive both the emotional intelligence variable with the indicators of the work itself, salary, promotion, supervision, and co-workers. Satisfied employees will work hard and give their best because employees are satisfied with what they have received from the company

Organizational commitment had a significant effect on OCB. Employees give a good perception of the organizational commitment variable with three indicators, namely affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. The conclusion that can be obtained is that increasing employee organizational commitment will also increase OCB in PT. Jemla Ferry Employees, Ketapang Banyuwangi Branch. High organizational commitment will influence and encourage OCB behavior by employees, because employees who are highly committed feel proud and have a sense of belonging to the company.

Recommendations for PT. Jemla Ferry are expected to maintain and improve the factors that can increase employee OCB behavior. And for the next researcher, the results of this

study are expected to be used as a reference for further research. In addition, you can change or add other variables such as organizational culture, personality or workload if you want to make research that is almost similar

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